

Impact of Multi-Generational Team Conflict, Coordination and Personality Types on their Team Performance

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Article Info	Abstract
<p><i>Article History</i></p> <p>Received: June 14, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: January 17, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Coordination, Team Performance, Multigenerational Teams, Team Conflict, Personality types</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5866761</p>	<p><i>Workforce teams in today's organizations comprises of employees belonging to multiple generations. Instead of going on the back foot, organizations need to take benefit from these employees by using them as edge over competitors. By utilizing qualitative research methods, twelve in-depth interviews were taken from three different hospitals of District Nowshera for investigating multigenerational team reasons for conflict along with level of their performance and coordination. This research indicated that actions, approaches, and preferences of multigenerational teams are affected by their past, financial, societal, and educational backgrounds which results in lack of coordination and decline in their performance. This research qualitatively enlightens the expectations gap as the basic reason for stress and conflicts between multigenerational employees. Qualitative analysis is the novel element of the research as till now research done on this area was quantitative in nature. This study will provide potential strategies for narrowing the gap among multigenerational teams.</i></p>

Introduction

At the turn of this century, organizations have four to five generation of employees. Kupper Schmidt (2000), defined generation to be comprises of people born nearly between similar time periods of two decades each. He enlightens it to be an "identifiable group that shares birth, years, age, location, and significant life events at critical developmental stages". Presently, five distinctive generations are working in organizations (Lieber, 2010; Twenge, 2010). These generations include, people born from 1925 to 1944 that are known as Traditionals, which are highly disciplined and self-sacrificing. Baby Boomers, comprising of people born from 1945 to 1964 that are optimistic and loyal to work (Notter, 2007), Generation X, including people born from 1965 to 1980 who likes to work independently (Cennamo & Gardner, 2008), Generation Y, including people born from 1981 to 2000 that are competitive and hard workers and Generation Z, including people born since 2001 which are multi-talented and prefers to be on many screens at one time (Eisner & Harvey, 2009; Levit, 2015).

Currently, the altering nature of organizations with respect to demographics, economy, cultural and technological aspects has catalyzed consideration towards workplace age dynamics (Finkelstein et al., 2015). On the other end of working age spectrum, current youth employees show difference in expectation of diversified career and new technologies. The latest generation Y and the upcoming generation Z have different opinions regarding work and lives. Distinctive conflict has been observed among Baby boomers and gen-X and Y, (Kaye et al. 2003). All of these generations have different perceptions, desires, norms, talents and behaviors, therefore different frames are needed for maintaining their work life balance. Lee Hecht Harrison (2007), in his survey stated that in every organization, more than 60 percent of teams is experiencing intergenerational conflict. When former and later generations work together they saw their differences and automatically attribute negative perceptions for others because they are not aware of inbuilt differences of individuals due to born in different generations. Research on work ethics and communication gap between multigenerational teams is limited (Crickenberger 2011; Kaye et al. 2003; Meriac et al. 2010). Hence the most demanding area of research after exploration of different generations is coexistence of these generations and its performance outcomes. This area of research need to be acknowledged due to differences in work style, key characteristics, behaviors and experiences of different generations, (Crickenberger 2011; Pitt-Catsouphes and Matz-Costa 2009).

Numerous occupations currently began to report generational diversity and its inferences for betterment of workplace e.g. lawyers (Foley and LeFevre 2001), librarians (Matesic 2009), and nurses, (Broom 2010; Leiter et al. 2010; Wilson et al. 2008). Multigenerational teams if not managed well may result in threats like employees' dissatisfaction, conflicts and turnover (Crickenberger 2011). These threats can be overcome by understanding each generation values and work styles. Studies regarding multigenerational discrimination and similar court hearings are very less in comparison to more types of discrimination, (Finkelstein & Truxillo, 2013). There is an immense need to inspect how multigenerational diversity affects the retention and performance of academic

work environment, predominantly health sector. It not only comprises of doctors and nurses who save lives but also consists of general and administrative staff, who may train the professional staff. Twenge and Campbell (2008), argued that one psychosocial feature of multigenerational workplace is rapidly increasing demand for productivity in least resources. This demand results in building pressure, stress and conflicts among employees. The basic reason behind diversified teams' failure, therefore, might be lack of coordination instead of participation (Kannan Srikanth, Sarah Harvey and Randall Peterson, 2016). Hence research is needed to analyze the level of social coordination among diversified teams, so to find out whether it impacts diversified team performance or some other factors are responsible for positive or negative team performance. This research is therefore intended to find the differences in personalities and generations among teams of health sector and analyzing the reasons of conflict among them and finally ending with ideas of enhancing their performance. Previously researchers' main focus while investigating diverse teams' remains constrained to gender or racial difference qualities and concentrated solely on local organizations, mostly to one particular firm only (Hajro A. Cristina B. Gibson, Pudelko M. 2017). The research gap is also taken from the work of (Michael S. North & Susan T. Fiske, 2015), that suggested managing multigenerational conflicts for handling upcoming generation Z by exploring and implementing appropriate management technique for better understanding the generational differences and resolving the issues for taking effective and efficient contribution from the multi-generational teams. This study will help in reducing clashes among multigenerational teams; so to minimize stress and conflicts among employees and increasing organizational performance. Additionally it will help in understanding difference of personalities and perceptions with respect to different generations and will help in minimizing the communication and coordination gap among multigenerational teams, so to give optimum performance as a team consisting of diversified members. This gives rise to the following problem statement; *"Waning team performance due to different personalities, lack of coordination and increased conflicts among multigenerational teams"*

1.1. Research Objectives

- i. To analyze the effect of different personalities with respect to multi-generational teams and their impact on health sector performance.
- ii. To investigate the level of communication and coordination among teams of doctors and general staff with same generation of employees and with multigenerational employees.
- iii. To minimize stress and conflicts among multigenerational teams and increasing their acceptability for each other, so to retain talented staff from all generations and save maximum lives.

1.2. Research Questions

- i. Do the personality's differences with respect to multi-generations affect the team performance of hospitals?
- ii. Does coordination gap in teams comprising of multi-generational staff is greater than teams belonging to similar generations?
- iii. How team performance can be increased by taking generational diversity practices as a competitive advantage at health sector?

Literature Review

This review of literature explains generational cohorts in today's workplace and examines employees' personality, attitude and work styles in health sector. Overlapping or complementary attitudes of employees' results in synergy that benefits the organization but differences between these generations negatively impact organizational performance. McCrindle and Wolfinger (2009) explained generation to be a cluster of individuals, born in same era, made and affected by similar times by going through similar happenings, styles and progresses of that specific time. The four kinds of generations, currently existing in work environment are Traditionals, Baby Boomers, Gen-X and Gen-Y.

The upcoming table shows that each generation has diverse opinion of work, ability, and relationships. It is difficult to understand a different perspective and each generation has erratic goals and views about work.

Table: 01 Mixture of Perspectives adapted from Laurel, 2005; Buahene, and Kovary, 2009

Characteristics	Traditionalists	Baby Boomers	Gen-X	Gen-Y
Outlook	Practical	Optimistic	Skeptical	Hopeful
Work Ethic	Dedicated	Driven	Balanced	Determined
Authority	Polite	Respectful	Love/Hate	Unimpressed
Leadership	Hierarchy	Consensus	Competence	Pull Together

Relationships	Personal Sacrifice	Personal Gratification	Reluctant to Commit	Inclusive
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2.1. Social Identity Theory and Multi-Generations

This study is stemmed in social identity theory as the foundation for the multi-generational construct, which is developed by Tajfel and Turner (1979), to comprehend the psychosomatic basis of in-group differences. Its key dimensions are related self-categorization, in-group differences, social identity and societal match. The underlying basic elements are classification, identification, comparison and psychological distinctiveness. According to Turner, Brown and Tajfel (1979), in group preference alludes to any inclination to prefer the in group on out group. In-group inclination alludes to oppressive conduct that conveys progressive advancement to group identity.

2.2. Multigenerational Teams Coordination and Conflict

In recent era, generational clashes are even more than previous decades; therefore managing people with different backgrounds have become more difficult too. Marcie (2009), concluded that employees' personality, work style, key characteristics and behaviors are molded by age factors. Therefore age impacts individual commitment, performance and output. In case of hospitals employees, i.e., doctors, nurses, general staff, their commitment increases with increase of experience and age. However this doesn't hold true according to Institute for Employment Studies that indicates feeling valued at job is a boosting element for commitment, therefore 50 and above age employees feel less valued and little involvement in organizations than employees under age of 30.

[Duchscher and Cowin \(2004\)](#), argued that diverse generations have diverse experiences in their past career and educational backgrounds. These experiences describe preferences about how different generations like to be instructed by their executives. Zamzow (2009), mentioned adjusting to change as the major challenge for older and younger generations due to change in personality traits during the career cycle. Thus executives must be trained for commendably dealing with differences and mentoring team players, especially in health sector where priority is saving lives of people rather than employees status. Efficient teams can reach to optimal results by harnessing diverse generations, their skills and expertise.

Gursoy, D., Maier, T. a., & Chi, C. G. (2008), concluded in their research that organizations would be less dynamic if the multiple expectations of teams belonging to different personalities and generational groups are not recognized and accomplished. Specifically he inspected the way managers belonging to Baby Boomers treat Gen X and Gen Y workers, and vice versa. As when different generations work together collaboratively, there will be various ways of treatment, i.e. old workers may prefer open heart surgery while young doctors may prefer laser treatment. McCaffree, J. (2007), argued workplace conflicts to be based upon misunderstandings between people of different generations. He observed individuals to be quick in faulting other generations who get recognition when they remain unsuccessful in achieving their personal objectives like promotion, bonuses and incentives. If individuals of one generation continually fault employees of other generation for failing to achieve their aspirations it will result in organizational disharmony in the hospitals along with dis-satisfied patients and bad repute of hospitals.

2.3. Multi-generational Personality Differences

Deal, J. J., Altman, D. G., & Rogelberg, S. G. (2010), concluded that although every generation of employees is distinctive and respectable with different personality traits, therefore each view others according to their own experiences and prospects. Management of health sector must convince people from diverse generational groups to judge each other more decidedly to evade intergenerational disharmony, i.e., giving time and way to deal with patients will be different in doctors belonging to different generations. It's not important to find what isolates them but rather it is important to revise their perceptions of one another so that together they can have a major effect in their associations and health sector performance.

Greene & Kelly (2005), deduced in their article that distinctions in personalities, generational qualities, practices, and states of mind can possibly make huge clash in the work environment. Young generational nurses may prefer extra care of patients while senior nurses may prefer less pampering of patients. Two noteworthy wellsprings of contention in today's surroundings are the apparent contrasts in hard working attitudes among generations and utilization of innovation. Hart K.A. (2006), suggested it's preferable to held similar work prospects, measures and processes. Accommodating generational preferences for mentoring, inspiring, collaborating, and resolving conflicts might increase team performance. Cran, C., (2010), said that employing such communication approaches that may work effectively for diverse personalities and generation employees is a challenge for current leaders. Thoughtfulness to communicate dissimilarities and preferences among different generations may help in bridging gaps and generating solutions that appeal to each generational value. Coordination must also assure to be comprehended for reducing misunderstandings among teams and enhancing performance.

2.4. Multigenerational Team Performance

Bottom line expansions in both returns and employee retention are found due to skills and competencies of older workers with satisfactory performance, (North & Hershfield, 2014). Also there is no enough trained young teams available at this time for replacing the performance standard of retiring old workers (Paullin, 2014; Phillips & Siu, 2012). Nevertheless, old generation workers have greater chances of disability resulting in sudden loss for the organizations by recruitment of trained worker in replacement and hence decrease organizational performance (Neumark, Song, & Button, 2015). That's the case with young doctors who don't have vast experience of major operations therefore are not suitable to replace the experienced doctors even after being specialized in the same field. Intrinsic workplace satisfaction rises with age while extrinsic satisfaction i.e., workplace growth decline with increase of age (Kooij, De Lange, Jansen, Kanfer, & Dikkers, 2011). Therefore a mix blend of all generations is necessary for satisfying more and more patients and establishing good will of hospitals.

Intergenerational resource tension is the basic barrier for satisfaction in organization with multigenerational teams. Interdependence among workers initiates stress and conflict that results in decrease of organizational performance (Birditt, Miller, Fingerma, & Lefkowitz, 2009; Glick & Fiske, 2011; North & Fiske, 2013a, b) such generational conflicts are specifically higher in swiftly aging, renovated organizations with increased employees interdependence and equity fires (Lee & Mason, 2011; North & Fiske, 2012). Therefore for enhancing multigenerational organization performance these intergenerational tensions must be converted into satisfactory work environment i.e. operating the patient by a team belonging to different generational doctors and general staff so they may work together by forgetting their intergenerational tensions for saving patient life.

Methodology

Realism perspective was used in research with the belief that reality exists independent of human mind filters and beliefs and is critical to know the reality with certainty. Exploratory research design was followed, in which literature was unfolded step wise around the basic phenomenon for answering the research questions.

A total sum of twelve in-depth interviews was taken, as in-depth interviews provide sufficient flexibility to the respondent to focus on what is important to them (Patton, 2002; Robson, 2002; Rubin & Rubin, 2005).

Doctors, general staff i.e., Nurses, Radiology department and administrative staff of combined military hospital (CMH), district health quarter (DHQ) and Cantonment Hospital Nowshera were selected as sample for obtaining broad range of different viewpoints as possible. Purposive sampling (Patton, 2002) was used to insure this variation that was sought through inclusion of variety of participants within the population (Hospitals of KPK) from district Nowshera.

All interviews were different in their information as they proceeded with the participant's direction. On average each interview lasted in 50 minutes. Most of the interviews were held at participant's location except 1 interview, which was conducted through internet voice chat and rest of others were in person.

Notes were taken during the interview and a summary of key points from the interview was made and shown to the interviewee for review and accuracy. Afterwards transcripts were generated from those interview notes and summaries.

Analysis

Data was analyzed by using Nvivo V-10 during the process of data collection, where information obtained from one interview was incorporated into subsequent interviews.

First step was the open coding process in which transcripts resulting from each interview were used to generate list of codes (Rubin & Rubin, 2005), into three main categories. All those passages that were relevant to the three main themes of the research were labeled in a short descriptive code i.e., if the passage keep on revolving around personality dimensions, i.e., perception, status, self-efficacy and motivation, then the main theme code given was multigenerational personality.

In next step when entire transcripts were coded, then those codes were summarized for overall content and tentative relationships between codes were identified. After making summary of codes, relationships were further explored and codes were realigned into a hierarchy of codes and sub codes e.g. the sub codes for the main theme of multigenerational coordination and performance were multigenerational values, leadership competencies and working style.

Frequency tables were formed for each sub code within the main codes. All the codes were punched into spreadsheet with rows for each point and columns for each respondent.

Table 02: Representing themes along with response frequency

Where YD means young doctors, OD stand for old doctors, YGS means young general staff and OGS means old general staff.

Main Theme 1: Multigenerational Team's Personality					
Themes	YD	OD	YGS	OGS	Total
<i>Generational Perception</i>	xx	xx	xx	xxx	09

<i>Generational Personality</i>	xx	xx	xx	x	07
<i>Position & Status</i>	xx	x	xx	xx	07
<i>Self-Efficacy</i>	xx	x	x	x	05
<i>Autonomous Motivation</i>	x	x	x	x	04
Main Theme 2: Multigenerational Team's Coordination and Conflicts					
<i>Technology oriented training</i>	xx	x	xx	x	06
<i>Performance or Functional Conflict</i>	x	xxx	xx	x	07
Main Theme 3: Multigenerational Team's Satisfaction & Performance					
<i>Multigenerational Values</i>	Xx	xx	xxx	xx	09
<i>Leadership Competency</i>	xx	xx	xx	xx	08
<i>Working Style</i>	xx	x	x	xx	06

4.1. Themes Related to Multigenerational Team's Personality

4.1.1. Generational Personality

One of the key determinants of individuals want from work is generational personality, which vary from person to person and generation to generation. It demonstrates their desirous workplace environment and conditions for being satisfied. Some of the respondent views regarding generational personality are as follows;

Employee wants and desires from work environment alter generation wise because of different personalities and key characteristics of employees, i.e. young doctors need recognition and old doctors need authority (OD: 01)

One generational doctors might have difficulty in understanding other generation doctors personalities and priorities which in turn becomes stressful and conflicting to work with, which in turn results in different associations of young and old doctors within same hospital. (YD: 01)

Traditional and Baby boomer employees have rigid personalities, specifically for the decisions they made. They neither share the strategies behind the order nor do they take any feedback from employees. (YGS: 02)

The basic problem with young workers is that they don't have tolerance element in their personality, due to their non-consistent nature; they keep on altering their treatment style without waiting for the outcome of one treatment (OGS: 03)

This difference of personality must be overcome by coaching and mentoring of all staff members so to work together for saving lives and enhancing hospital repute, irrespective of their differences.

4.1.2. Multigenerational Position and Status in Organization

Although organizations try to regulate status and job positions among multigenerational teams, conflicts are still found on generational position and status in the organization, as mentioned by respondents;

Employees' job positions largely influence their productivity, perceptions and attitude. Authoritative position employees in hospitals give great importance to non-financial recognition for their performance while line-level workers value financial incentives more than non-financial recognition (OGS: 01)

Upper status of a young doctor may turns the senior doctor into inferiority complex that results in decline in his own performance by not giving proper time to patients and absentees from job which consequently decline performance of the hospital due to the coordination gap between higher authorities and middle level managers. (YD: 01)

Level of commitment with organization increases with workers generations and status at job, doctors belonging to Silent generation and Baby boomers are found more committed on head of department positions i.e. neurology, medical, child care etc. than on associate positions. (OD: 02)

Older employees want to have good status jobs, if they are provided an opportunity to work below a young boss; they either don't perform well or quit the job by considering it their disgrace. (YGS: 03)

Such conflicts of status quo can be minimized by assigning all generational doctors and general staff different responsibilities which are interdependent on each other.

4.1.3. Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy means people beliefs about their skills for performing well; it increases employee motivation for being more productive. Respondents' common thoughts about this are as under;

Multigenerational doctors ponder, integrate, and assess information about their skills and talents to compose their efforts. (OD: 01)

Doctors who have strong self-efficacy, exerts significant effort for becoming the optimum performer. (YD: 02)
 Organization can take benefit from the self-efficacy of multigenerational workers by increasing their morale and commitment to work together for enhancing hospital repute and reliability among patients and general public.

4.1.4. Autonomous Motivation and Generational Difference

Another compromising element of multigenerational teams is autonomous motivation. Individuals from different generations possess unique ideas for resolving identical problems. Due to the personality and generational grouping, employees become least motivated to give their even better ideas for the growth of other generational group over them, thus results in decreased autonomous motivation and innovation. The same was mentioned by; *Multigenerational blending may results in creating stress and conflicts in organization due to the difference of personality, characteristics, work style, status, perceptions and expectations from organization. (OGS: 01)*
Multigenerational mixing results in creating stress and conflict in hospitals by grouping teams into ‘us vs. them’ mentality i.e. old and young doctors association (OD: 01)

Such conflicts must be converted into functional conflict for the hospitals where multigenerational employees work collaboratively for making better image of their hospital in comparison to other hospitals of same locality.

4.1.5. Perception of Other Generations

Generational perception is regarded as basic factor of crating conflicts among multigenerational teams. Such perceptions contain negative and positive expectations from different generations i.e. perception that Traditionals and Baby boomers are least deserving to be selected. According to respondents;

Individuals over a certain age are not able to contribute effectively in job either as doctors or as general staff of hospitals due to their low stamina... (YD: 01)

Interviews data suggested that Boomers have negative perception of Generation X and Generation Y.

Boomer employees think that younger employees don't have self-potential and are dependent on technology. They neither have work ethics nor do they have the experience to manage stress situations during operations. (OD: 02)

Gen X employees perceives workers of Gen Y not to be able of understanding the nature of task but to be quick in learning new technologies. (OGS: 03)

Older employees prefer older colleagues work as more reliable than of youth colleagues, due to which executive position promotion chances are greater for older workers than young teams. (YD: 02)

Multigenerational perception should be positive for collaborative and progressive work environment. Therefore both young and old doctors and general staff must be trained to work together by understanding each other differences.

4.2. Themes Related to Multigenerational Coordination and Conflicts

4.2.1. Mutigenerational Functional or Performance Conflict

Understanding generational differences can be used as an instrument for improving employee's satisfaction, performance and innovation. Perceptions of doctors and general staff regarding older employees in their interviews have mixed comments such as;

...my negative association for older employees is based on aging effects on memory and capability of working... (YGS: 02)

....my positive association with older employees is based on reliable way of working due to experience in the same field...(OGS: 02)

....my negative association with older doctors is concerned with stamina demanding operations i.e. operations of 24 hours or more...(YD: 01)

...my negative association with younger workers is their inconsistency and low patience to wait for the outcomes of treatment given...(OD: 03)

Such conflicts must be overcome for having different treatment styles and thus able of addressing need of diverse patients.

4.2.2. Multigenerational Coordination in Technology Oriented Training

Training is strongly related with increased earnings and productivity. It is essential for hospitals as Traditional and Baby boomers have reached retirement stage and generation Y even Z graduates are getting ready to join the labor force. Mutigenerational teams and technologies training are continuously changing in every decade, for meeting the needs of this evolution several issues need to be addressed. As said by both young and old staff; *E-learning is implemented by various organizations for meeting advanced training demands of raising technology as it provide access to advanced training techniques from various sources all over the world. Such computer-based training seems easier to adopt for generation X and Y doctors and general staff, who are familiar with technology from their childhood but challenging for traditionals and Baby boomer workers, who haven't yet embraced to online training instead of traditional training seminars. (YD: 03)*

Numerous national and multinational hospitals spend huge amount of money yearly for technical and developmental training of their workers. Thus it's necessary for training providers to give a kind of training, fruitful for multigenerational teams. (YGS: 01)

Travelling from typewriter to PCs, web, projector and multimedia in less than 15 years indicated the swiftness of technical advancement adopted by organizations. Therefore farmer workers must squeeze technology.. (OGS: 02)

There is an exceptional shift from greater numeral of old and experienced employees to a smaller numeral of highly technological, but inexperienced employees. Therefore workers belonging to any generation must be provided with demand of time skills and training for the betterment of health sector.

4.3. Themes Related to Multigenerational Satisfaction and Performance

4.3.1. Multigenerational Values

Every generation has its own values, key characteristics and capabilities; multigenerational teams therefore have its own issues regarding coordination and cooperation of employees. Similar thoughts were given by;

Younger doctors value the involvement in team tasks and professional conferences for generating competency training. (YD: 01)

Difference in multigenerational employees values act as the root cause of conflict in hospitals. But if handled well, they can become source of Hospitals growth. (OGS: 02)

To understand the value of employees' is vital for authoritative position staff members, as their job performance is based on the satisfaction of their values at hospitals. (OGS: 03)

Knowledge regarding multigenerational employees work value differences may help in making collaborative work environment and may have significant implications on health sector performance.

4.3.2. Multigenerational leadership Competencies

Understanding the capabilities and skills of multigenerational teams is essential for employers to maintain a working environment that nurture their competencies and talents to work more effectively as team members. As concluded by;

Younger doctors tend to value leadership skills, competencies, flexibility, effectiveness and ethics more than older doctors therefore are found as more influential leaders. (YD: 02)

Significant differences are present across generational cohorts of authoritative staff members for their level of "competencies". (OGS: 01)

Older employees believe in autocratic style of leadership, i.e. like their solely decisions to be implemented while young general staff members believe in democratic leadership style where every staff member has the right of performing accordingly (YGS: 03)

The leading abilities of all generations if work together can achieve any milestone of way, therefore instead of hesitations of working together, the organization may take advantage of multiple leading styles.

4.3.3. Working Style

The working style of employees varies from generation to generation due to different brought ups i.e. traditionals prefers top-down bureaucratic approach working style. As the views given by;

Traditional employees' beliefs that control must be rationalized, therefore they adopted bureaucratic management style of working. (OGS: 02)

Generation Y doctors want to have clear command and organizational support along with tractability and independence for achieving their tasks. (YD: 02)

Old generation workers like to take the decision by oneself only while young generation employees believe in participative decision making. (YGS: 03)

Adopting innovative HRM strategies can be helpful for successful retention and productivity of multigenerational employees. Bureaucratic work style must not be opted for dealing with young generation workers, therefore leadership styles must become flexible for resolving conflicts of work style among multigenerational teams so to create higher work life balance.

Discussion

This research indicated that stress and conflict situation due to generational gap is found among the teams of health sector, i.e., hospital staff. Employees were found good individually, but avoid group work and cooperation especially in case of multi-generational group if made, i.e. arranging seminars, adopting technological training, attending professional conferences etc. It's a fact that all generations of workers are distinctive, valuable, and exceptional. Due to which they have different perceptions regarding each other. Therefore the hospitals management must confirm that employees belonging to diverse age groups may understand each other's differences in a positive manner for avoiding multigenerational dis-harmony.

Conclusion

Interviews results indicated that traditionals and Baby boomer workers have more positive expectations from their similar generation employees than their younger colleagues and vice versa; this result is aligned with the research findings of Furunes and Mykletun (2010). This research helps in in-depth knowledge of multigenerational variances and resemblances, coordination gap, difference of personality and provides ways of increasing employees' performance by turning those differences as opportunities for success.

It can be concluded that work values of employees differ from generation to generation, for making a productive and pleasant workplace, these differences should be overcome by the leaders, this is consistent with the research conclusion of (Zemke et al., 2000). Generational conflicts can be resolved by correcting employee's misperceptions from each other so that together they can make a big difference in their organizations. Different generation workers should perceive each other positively; rely on each other's work and try to respect the difference of values so that they may become able of accepting the upcoming generation of employees i.e. Gen Z in year after 2020 and so on.

Recommendations

The first step to be taken by the management of hospitals should be to ask the staff members, their needs and preferences of working effectively. The management should choose people with varied backgrounds and perspectives to work together in any sort of harsh or normal working conditions with the priority of providing best quality education. Hospitals may create work environments, of such a way in which all the generations employee opinions are valued. The hospitals management should include representatives from all generations in some capacity on boards and councils so to satisfy all generation workers by giving equal priority.

Another way to minimize the coordination and cooperation gap can be offering a mentoring program for all the staff members, on tackling generational diversity for the betterment of health sector in a variety of formats i.e. classroom style, online, experiential, interactive, and in staff meetings, this will facilitate knowledge transfer, as suggested by (Roberts, B.W. 2006).

One of the useful leadership tool for minimizing generational conflicts can be appreciative inquiry that means promoting positively monitoring employees instead of critical evaluation. This may help in lowering the conflicts caused by misperception of favoring certain generation of employees over others.

5.1. Limitations and Directions for Future Research

Like every research work this study is not free from limitations. One of the basic shortcomings of this research is that purposive sampling was done for analyzing result therefore results cannot be generalized to the hospitals outside KPK. Another limitation can be the study is based on qualitative technique of analysis i.e., interviews, results might vary if analysis will be done by quantitative technique i.e. questionnaires.

A more demanding future research direction could be comparison between international health sector multigenerational teams hospitals, so to explore the difference in coordination, conflicts and personalities of different generational teams across the globe and work on overcoming the clashes for increasing organizational performance not only in health sector but in various other sectors like education, manufacturing and financial institutions.

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